

COUNCIL on LIBRARY and INFORMATION RESOURCES

Annual Report 2013–2014

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Annual Report 2013–2014

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The Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR) is an independent, nonprofit organization that forges strategies to enhance research, teaching, and learning environments in collaboration with libraries, cultural institutions, and communities of higher learning. CLIR aspires to transform the information landscape to support the advancement of knowledge.

CLIR promotes forward-looking collaborative solutions that transcend disciplinary, institutional, professional, and geographic boundaries in support of the public good. In pursuing its mission, CLIR is committed to building trust, retaining independence, fostering collaboration, cultivating effective leadership, and capitalizing on strategic opportunities.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The following institutions and individuals provide crucial support for the activities and programs of the Council on Library and Information Resources (as of June 30, 2014).

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Click on image to be taken to an interactive map showing CLIR sponsors and DLF members.

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Temple University Library
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Texas Tech University
Trinity University
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Tulane University
Union College
The University of Alabama Libraries
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Yale University

DLF Members (as of June 30, 2014)

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Bibliotheca Alexandrina
Brown University
Bryn Mawr College
California Digital Library
California Institute of Technology
Clemson University
Coalition for Networked Information
Colgate University
Columbia University
Cornell University
Dartmouth College
Emory University
Florida State University
Georgetown University
George Washington University
Georgia Institute of Technology
Georgia State University
Harvard University
Indiana University
Inter-university Consortium for Political
and Social Research
The Joint Information Systems Committee
Johns Hopkins University
Lafayette College
Library of Congress
Los Alamos National Laboratory
Research Library
Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Montana State University
National Library of Medicine
New York Public Library
New York University
North Carolina State University Libraries
Northeastern University
Northwestern University
OCLC Research
The Ohio State University
Oregon State University
Pennsylvania State University, University
Libraries
Princeton Theological Seminary
Princeton University Library
Purdue University
Rhodes College
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Temple University
Texas A & M University
University of Arizona
The University of British Columbia
University of California, Berkeley
University of California, Irvine
University of California, Los Angeles
University of California, San Diego
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Champaign
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Chapel Hill
University of North Texas
University of Notre Dame
University of Pennsylvania
University of Southern California
University of Tennessee
University of Texas at Austin
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The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
The Brown Foundation, Inc.
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Howard and Mathilde Rovelstad
Institute of Museum and Library Services
Library of Congress
David Rumsey

Directors July 1, 2013–June 30, 2014

DAN COHEN*
Digital Public Library of America

PAUL COURANT
University of Michigan

KURT DE BELDER
Leiden University

MARK DIMUNATION
Library of Congress

DARBY ENGLISH*
Clark Art Institute

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Modern Language Association

DAVID GIFT
Michigan State University

EMILIE GORDENKER*
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University of Washington

KARIN WITTENBORG
University of Virginia

** Elected April 2014*

*** Term concluded November 2013*

**** Term concluded April 2014*

Staff as of June 30, 2014

LIZZI ALBERT
Administrative Coordinator

ALICE BISHOP
Senior Program Officer

RACHEL FRICK
Director, Digital Library Federation

CHARLES HENRY
President

SHARON IVY WEISS
Chief Operating Officer

LOUISA KWASIGROCH
Senior Program Associate
Digital Library Federation

ADAM LEADER-SMITH
Administrative Associate

BRIAN LENY
Publications Manager

AMY LUCKO
Director of Program Data and Statistics

KATHLIN SMITH
Director of Communications

CHRISTA WILLIFORD
Director of Research and Assessment

JENA WINBERRY
Program Officer

Distinguished Presidential Fellows

MICHAEL EDSON
Smithsonian Institution

STEPHEN G. NICHOLS
Johns Hopkins University

BETHANY NOWVSKIE
University of Virginia

ELLIOTT SHORE
Association of Research Libraries

JOHN UNSWORTH
Brandeis University

LETTER from the PRESIDENT

Charles Henry
President

This year, CLIR celebrated two milestones: the 100th edition of *CLIR Issues* and the 20th anniversary of the Digital Library Federation (DLF). For *CLIR Issues* #100, I wrote an essay focusing on the themes that animated CLIR at its inception and persist to this day, as well as some of the more striking differences that define our contemporary mission. The article looked back to the first edition of *CLIR Issues* in 1998—the organization’s inaugural publication following the merger of the Council on Library Resources and the Commission on Preservation and Access. Many topics covered in that first issue remain integral to our mission, including the tensions between using analog materials as opposed to digital surrogates; the challenge of preserving our cultural record; exploring and defining the concept of a digital library; funding and sustaining technology-dependent projects; and developing new approaches to staffing and expertise in response to an evolving digital environment.

In light of these themes, it is not surprising that DLF was featured in that first newsletter. DLF had been formed only a few years earlier and its strategy was just starting to take shape. “Digital Library Federation Shapes its Program,” written by DLF’s first director, Don Waters, describes the program’s earliest activities, including DLF’s participation in the Making of America project, which highlighted the importance of metadata and the distinctions among various kinds of metadata. Don Waters also describes some of the site visits he made to better understand DLF member institutions and their activities pertaining to digital libraries, noting that in 1998:

Many projects have arisen in response not to institutional needs but to intense personal interests among library staff members, who worry that they will be left behind professionally and that their institutions will suffer competitively if they do not engage in digital library work. The projects resulting from such motivation are useful for the professional development of members of the library staff, but they are typically small and underfunded, and they lack the institutional backing that is essential if the work is to endure over time.

Since then, the scale of digital library projects has increased considerably, and collaboration is more widespread. Nonetheless, sustainability remains a critical issue, as does institutional support, and metadata is perhaps more at the forefront now than in the late 1990s.

From those early site visits that informed DLF's agenda, a flourishing program has evolved. The Digital Library Federation today attracts a growing membership and, through its annual Forum, convenes a national conversation that rigorously and candidly explores the chief issues and challenges of information technology in educational and cultural institutions. This year in Atlanta, the Forum attracted more than 400 participants, the largest number of attendees ever. More than 100 proposals were submitted—another record—and over 100 institutions were represented in the presentations, workshops, and poster sessions: a vibrant, collegial, and practical conference.

Because DLF brings together a variety of technology practitioners and project leaders, it serves CLIR as the practical linchpin for the execution of our vision. Without DLF, CLIR would not be able to instantiate the many ideas and concepts articulated in our reports and research. The Digital Library Federation connects CLIR to a world of thoughtful expertise that develops and maintains the digital ecology in which higher education thrives. We anticipate many more years of research, service, and leadership to an ever-growing constituency.

The most notable difference between the work of CLIR in 1998 and today is the creation of a framework in which all of our projects and programs are brought together and nested in an encompassing national context. Strengthening this framework is the focus of the [Committee on Coherence at Scale for Higher Education](#), established in 2012.

The committee was established as a national project based on an observation and a hypothesis. The observation is that we live in a time when several very large-scale digital projects are under way that represent nearly every facet of the cycle of academic knowledge. These facets include the creation and curation of data; long-term preservation; the growth of accessible digital libraries for research and pedagogy; publishing; the reuse and recombination of scholarship; and the production of new tools and applications that promote more sophisticated inquiry and methodologies. The hypothesis rests on the assumption that these projects, while valuable in and of themselves, would be extraordinary if developed as integrated elements of a new system in support of higher education, and, by extension, in service to the public good.

Put another way, the Committee on Coherence at Scale responds to a pervasive twenty-first century conundrum: that no single profession or agency can meaningfully manage the proliferating and unscripted surge of technology; and that the tradition of institutional competition has to be suspended, at least in part, to address the complexity of the digital revolution by providing the strategic leadership necessary to realize a new academic ecology.

Milestones, at their best, provide reason to pause and reflect on accomplishments as well as on the challenges ahead. The details and remarkable sweep of CLIR's activities in 2014 can be gleaned from this annual report. The intellectual road connecting 1998 to 2014 has been exhilarating, traveled always with the acknowledgment that we are privileged to work in, learn from, and influence a pivotal—and at times astonishing—turn in the nearly thousand-year venture of higher education.

Charles Henry
President
November 2014

360 people
attended the 2013
DLF Forum

\$3.95 million
granted in the
Hidden Collections
program

**CLIR'S
REACH**
this year

Over 200 CLIR
sponsors and DLF
members

39 attended the
2014 Leading
Change Institute in
Washington, DC

44 Postdoctoral
Fellows received
grants

17 Mellon
Dissertation
Fellowships
awarded

Four reports,
numerous blog posts,
and 6 newsletters
published

PROGRAMS and ACTIVITIES

July 1, 2013–June 30, 2014

DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Objective: Promote research, skill development, and collaboration to strengthen the digital infrastructure supporting all facets of the scholarly communication cycle.

Digital Library Federation Program

CLIR's Digital Library Federation program is a resource and catalyst for collaboration among digital library developers, project managers, and all who are invested in digital library issues. The DLF promotes work on digital library standards and best practice; research and data management; aggregation and preservation services for digital col-

lections; and digital library services that expand access to digital resources for research, teaching, and learning. DLF staff and activities are integral to other CLIR programs—from the CLIR/DLF Postdoctoral Fellowships in Data Curation to the Committee on Coherence at Scale for Higher Education.

The 2013 DLF Forum, held November 4–6 in Austin, Texas, had record attendance. The Forum is an important venue for the exchange of information that will lead to a better understanding of the elements and complexity of digital library evolution, as well as for collaboration on practical work.

The DLF maintains an active community website, with updates from its members, at <http://www.diglib.org>.

LINKS to more information

Click images to hear participants share their impressions of the 2013 Forum and what brought them there. Harrison Dekker of the University of California, Berkeley (top), and Gina Siesing of Bryn Mawr College (bottom).

E-Science/E-Research

The third E-Science Institute, cosponsored by DLF and DuraSpace, ran from December 2013–April 2014. The institute, first offered in late 2011 in collaboration with the Association for Research Libraries, was designed to help academic and research libraries develop a strategic agenda for e-research support, with a particular focus on the sciences.

Building on the success of the E-Science Institute, and responding to participants' desire for an ongoing support network for e-science practice, DLF launched the E-Research Peer Network Mentoring Group (ERPNUMG) in May 2014. ERPNUMG aims to develop a network of practitioners by fostering participant-directed learning and shared skill development. A select group of consultants works with participants to assess each institution's service layers and identify next steps for planning and implementing research data management services.

Study on Needs in Continuing Education for Managing Cultural Heritage Data

In September 2013, the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS) awarded CLIR a grant to examine federally mandated plans for open access and their implications for continuing education needs for libraries, museums, and other cultural heritage institutions. Under this grant, CLIR is conducting research in three areas. Part 1 involves a highly structured content analysis of select federal agency plans for supporting open access to data and publications, identifying the commonalities and differences among the plans with emphasis on access to data. Part 2 takes the results of the content analysis and traces its implications for IMLS program areas and the cultural heritage institutions they serve. Part 3 identifies gaps in continuing education opportunities for cultural heritage professionals, assessing the readiness of the current professional workforce and identifying how best to address the needs and close the gaps in the immediate and longer term. Final results will be released in summer 2015.

Committee on Coherence at Scale

CLIR established the **Committee on Coherence at Scale for Higher Education** in October 2012, in partnership with Vanderbilt University. The committee's charge is to examine emerging national-scale digital projects and

their potential to help transform higher education in terms of scholarly productivity, teaching, cost-efficiency, and sustainability. The Committee currently comprises **21 members**, including university and college presidents and provosts, heads of national education associations and other organizations, and

LINK to more information

What are some examples of national-scale digital projects? View "**FactSheets**," a series of one-page profiles on large-scale, multi-partner initiatives across the library and IT communities in higher education. Profiles are updated periodically.

library and i-school deans. The Committee meets twice yearly.

In April 2014, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation awarded two grants for Coherence projects. The first, a strategic planning grant, went to Vanderbilt University. The second, awarded to the University of Pittsburgh's i-School, supports a new **doctoral fellowship program for information sciences** students worldwide. The grant will support 10 iFellows, to be announced in late 2014 or early 2015, who will supplement the work of the COC with independent dissertation research.

LINK to more information

Click to watch a **brief video** about the aims of the **Committee on Coherence at Scale**.

SCHOLARSHIP and RESEARCH

Objective: Explore and assess new research methodologies, emerging fields of inquiry, intellectual strategies involving data gathering and collaboration, and modes of communication, including sharing of research data and publishing models, that are likely to define the next generation of scholars.

Postdoctoral Fellowship Program

CLIR's Postdoctoral Fellowship Program offers recent PhD graduates an opportunity to work on projects that forge and strengthen connections among library collections, educational technologies, and current research. The program was initiated a decade ago as the Postdoctoral Fellowships in Academic Libraries.

In 2012, with support from the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR broadened the program to incorporate

an emphasis on data curation: first, with the Postdoctoral Fellowships for Data Curation in the Sciences and Social Sciences, and second, with the Postdoctoral Fellowships for Data Curation in Medieval Studies. In October 2013, CLIR announced a new data curation track for early modern studies and in June 2014, a track for data curation in visual studies—both with support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation.

CLIR's Postdoctoral Fellows in Academic Libraries and the Data Curation Fellows share information

LINK to more information

View **video interviews** with participants and supervisors.

and experiences with one another. Together they gain a broad understanding of the importance of data and information management to the emerging research environment while becoming a cohort of highly skilled and deeply knowledgeable specialists.

The CLIR/DLF Postdoctoral Fellows summer seminar was held in July 2013 at Bryn Mawr College. The annual event is designed to introduce new fellows to the possibilities of the fellowship through ten days of seminar-style conversations, guest speakers, and discussions of readings about current issues in librarianship, research, and the academy.

Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives

Launched in 2008 with the support of The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR's Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Program supports efforts to expose unknown or underutilized cultural materials to communities of scholars, students, and other users who need them for their work. In December 2013, CLIR announced awards to 22 project recipients. In 2014, CLIR issued the program's seventh and final call for proposals.

Throughout the first half of 2014, CLIR staff engaged in discussions with the Mellon Foundation about a possible successor to the Hidden Collections program that would focus on digitizing, rather than cataloging. They consulted with experts in the broader community and conducted research about projects recently funded through national-level programs. These discussions have helped CLIR articulate the core values that will inform the design of the new initiative: transforming scholarship, exposing large quantities of rare and unique materials, encouraging deep inter-institutional collaboration, promoting sustainable practices, and maximizing open access to digital collections and metadata. CLIR expects to have further information about a successor program in December 2014.

LINK to more information

Read "[Un-Hidden Collections: CLIR's Seven-Year Experiment in Exposing Scholarly Resources and the Question of Digitization.](#)"

2013 Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Awards

Amherst College

Samuel French Theatre Archives \$144,300

Bok Tower Gardens

Cataloging the Vertical Files of the Anton Brees Carillon Library \$219,700

California Academy of Sciences

Frontier Science: Providing Access to the Early Scientific History of the American West in the Collections of the California Academy of Sciences \$50,600

Center for Jewish History

Expanding Access to American Jewish Archival Collections \$30,000

Columbia University

Makino Collection Film Ephemera and Rare Book Project \$380,500

Dayton Society of Natural History

The Lichliter Site Project: A Model for Revealing Hidden Archaeological Collections \$91,000

Erie Canal Museum

Canal Society of New York State Collection \$71,100

George Eastman House

Documenting Their Films: Hidden Collections of Four Independent Filmmakers \$155,900

The George Washington University

D.C. Africana Archives Project (DCAAP) \$495,900

Hagley Museum and Library

The David Sarnoff Collection Processing Project \$291,500

Kansas City Public Library

The Kansas City Stockyards Collection \$101,000

La MaMa Experimental Theatre Club

Cataloging La MaMa's Pushcart Years: A Unique History of the Off-Off Broadway Theatre Movement \$135,100

Lehigh University

Bridge and Building Forensics: Civil Engineering Archives at Lehigh University \$93,700

Maine State Museum

An American Mirror: Early Photograph Collections at the Maine State Museum \$145,600

The Newberry Library

Printing Specimens (1605-present) at the Newberry Library \$216,100

Princeton University

Princeton University Library's Latin American Ephemera Project \$199,800

San Diego Museum of Man

Cataloging Hidden Collections: San Diego Museum of Man's Archaeology, Archival and Photographic Collections \$240,500

Union College

Grass Roots Activism and the American Wilderness: Pioneers in the Twentieth Century Adirondack Park Conservation Movement \$164,600

University at Albany, SUNY

Building New Access Tools for the National Death Penalty Archive \$119,900

University at Buffalo, SUNY

Processing the Editorial and Business Records of Eleven Little Literary Magazine Archives in the Poetry Collection \$150,600

University of North Texas

Post-War Industry and Development of the Southwest Metroplex \$163,400

University of Washington Libraries

Discovering Modern China: University of Washington and University of British Columbia Collections \$183,500

Yellowstone Park Foundation

Using a Team Approach to Expose Yellowstone's Hidden Collections \$106,000

More detail on this year's funded projects can be found at <http://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/awards/for-2013>.

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships

In 2014, 17 graduate students were selected to receive Mellon Dissertation Fellowships. The fellowship program, initiated in 2002, is intended to help graduate students in the humanities and related social science fields pursue doctoral research using original sources and gain skill and creativity in using primary source materials in libraries, archives, museums, and related repositories. To date, the program has supported more than 160 graduate students who have carried out their dissertation research in public and private libraries and archives worldwide.

Workshops on Participatory Design in Academic Libraries

In June 2013, CLIR concluded its Workshops on Participatory Design in Academic Libraries program with a seminar at the University of Rochester. The seminar was an opportunity for participants of previous CLIR participatory design workshops to report on projects that they had undertaken at

their institutions using techniques learned from Nancy Fried Foster. Foster, previously professor of anthropology at the University of Rochester, had led the workshop series since 2007 and trained more than 250 participants. CLIR published a [report](#) on the final seminar in January 2014.

LEADERSHIP EDUCATION and CULTIVATION

Objective: Investigate and seek to define the skills and expertise needed to administer, inspire, and inform the next generation.

Leading Change Institute

CLIR and EDUCAUSE hosted the second Leading Change Institute (LCI) June 1-6, 2014. Thirty-nine participants joined deans Elliott Shore, executive director, Association of Research Libraries; and Joanne Kossuth, vice president for operations and CIO, Olin College of Engineering. Following the LCI, participants were invited to join deans Shore and Kossuth for regular monthly discussions, allowing them to continue exchanges beyond the Institute and to provide ongoing support and advice for one another.

Successor to the Frye Leadership Institute, LCI shares the same goal that inspired the Frye Institute: to prepare and develop the next generation of leaders in libraries, information services, and higher education by engaging those who seek to further develop their skills for the benefit of higher education.

Leading Change Institute Participants 2014

Andrea Beesing, Cornell University
Char Booth, Claremont Colleges
Debra Bucher, Vassar College
Michael Chapple, University of Notre Dame
Allan Chen, Menlo College
Jama Coartney, University of Virginia
Margaret Cohen, Boston College
Joseph Combs, Vanderbilt University
Niranjan Davray, Kenyon College
Emily Decker, Atlanta University Center, Robert W. Woodruff Library
Barbara DeFelice, Dartmouth College
Caleb Derven, University of Limerick
Laura Farwell Blake, Harvard University
Lisa Forrest, Hamilton College
Jennifer Green, University of Michigan
Beverly Guiry, Boston University
Joel Herndon, Duke University, Perkins Library
Curtis Hillegas, Princeton University
Patricia Hswe, Pennsylvania State University
Barbara Knauff, Dartmouth College
Elisa Lanzl, Smith College
Catherine Lavallee-Welch, University of Wisconsin-La Crosse
Joseph Mancini, Montgomery County Community College
Meris Mandernach, The Ohio State University
Timothy McGeary, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Sue Mehrer, Cambridge University Library
Laura Morse, Harvard University
Colleen Nagy, Case Western Reserve University
Brian Rossmann, Montana State University
Joseph Salem, The University of Akron
Michael Satut, Northwestern University
Joseph Shelley, University of Washington Bothell
Jeffrey Stanton, Syracuse University
Jeff Steely, Baylor University
Mark Sullivan, SUNY Geneseo
Laurie Sutch, University of Michigan
Michael Thompson, University of Southern Queensland
Frances Yarger, University of Pittsburgh
Maurice York, North Carolina State University

Chief Information Officers Group

CLIR's Chief Information Officers Group is composed of 29 directors of organizations that have merged their library and technology units on liberal arts college and university campuses.

The group, which meets semi-annually, devoted its December 2013 meeting to a discussion of the future of library and information technology services (LITS), and how their organizations should position themselves for that future. The discussion formed the basis for a white paper, written by CIOs Richard Holmgren of Allegheny College and Gene Spencer of Ursinus College, that CLIR issued in September 2014. *The Changing Landscape of Library and Information Services: What Presidents, Provosts, and Finance Officers Need to Know* explores emerging opportunities for colleges and universities, the potential role of LITS organizations in realizing that potential, and the core competencies that LITS organizations will need to support positive institutional change in the decade ahead.

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group Members

(as of 6/30/14)

Param Bedi, Bucknell University
Frank Cervone, Purdue University Calumet
Jim Cubit, Lake Forest College
Greg Diment, Kalamazoo College
Megan Fitch, Beloit College
Ronald Griggs, Kenyon College
Lee Hisle, Connecticut College
Rick Holmgren, Allegheny College
Robert Johnson, Rhodes College
Todd Kelley, Carthage College
Kenneth Kochien, Colby-Sawyer College
Paul Mattson, Luther College
Pam McQuesten, Southwestern University
Michael Miller, California Polytechnic State University
Kathy Monday, University of Richmond

Rick Provine, DePauw University
Ravi Ravishanker, Wellesley College
Robert Renaud, Dickinson College
Vicki Sells, Sewanee: The University of the South
Gina Siesing, Bryn Mawr College
Justin Sipher, St. Lawrence University
David Smallen, Hamilton College
Carol Smith, DePauw University
Gene Spencer, Ursinus College
Bruce Taggart, Lehigh University
John Unsworth, Brandeis University
Gene Wiemers, Bates College
Alex Wirth-Cauchon, Mount Holyoke College
Frank Wojcik, The College at Brockport, State University of New York

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Janetta Pegues, a library science student at the University of Wisconsin-Madison, was awarded the 2014 Rovelstad Scholarship. Pegues became interested in international librarianship while volunteering at a school in Gonaives, Haiti.

Instituted in 2002, the Rovelstad Scholarship encourages library students who have an interest in international library work by enabling them to attend the World Library and Information Congress, the annual meeting of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. The 2014 meeting was held in Lyon, France.

PUBLICATIONS

- *Born Digital: Guidance for Donors, Dealers, and Archival Repositories*, by Gabriela Redwine et al. October 2013.
- *Research Data Management: Principles, Practices, and Prospects*, November 2013.
- *The Survival of American Silent Feature Films: 1912-1929*, by David Pierce. December 2013.
- *CLIR Annual Report, 2012-2013*. December 2013.
- *Participatory Design in Academic Libraries: New Reports and Findings*, edited by Nancy Fried Foster. February 2014.
- *CLIR Issues* 94–99.

FELLOWS

2014–2015 Postdoctoral Fellows

New Fellows

Laura Aydelotte

PhD English, University of Chicago
Host: University of Pennsylvania

Michael Bales

PhD Biomedical Informatics,
Columbia University
Host: Weill Cornell Medical College

Meaghan Brown

PhD English Literature, Florida State
University
Host: Folger Shakespeare Library

Scout Calvert

PhD History of Consciousness,
University of California, Santa Cruz
Host: University of California, Los
Angeles

Morgan Daniels

PhD Philosophy in Information,
University of Michigan
Host: Vanderbilt University

Rachel Deblinger

PhD History, University of California,
Los Angeles
Host: University of California, Santa
Cruz

Anne Donlon

PhD English, The City University of
New York
Host: Emory University

Annie Johnson

PhD History, University of Southern
California
Host: Lehigh University

Emily McGinn

PhD Comparative Literature,
University of Oregon
Host: Lafayette College

Monica Mercado

PhD History, University of Chicago
Host: Bryn Mawr College

Paige Morgan

PhD English and Textual Studies,
University of Washington
Host: McMaster University

Alice Motes

PhD Sociology, University of
California, Irvine
Host: University of Minnesota

Rikk Mulligan

PhD American Studies, Michigan State
University
Host: Association of Research Libraries

Tim Norris

PhD Environmental Studies,
University of California at Santa Cruz
Host: University of Miami

Charlotte Nunes

PhD English, University of Texas
at Austin
Host: Southwestern University

Jessica Otis

PhD History, University of Virginia
Host: Carnegie Mellon University

Philip Palmer

PhD English, University of
Massachusetts Amherst
Host: University of California, Los
Angeles

Alicia Peaker

PhD English Literature with Certificate
in Women's Studies,
Northeastern University
Host: Middlebury College

Sarah Pickle

PhD Comparative Literature, Cornell
University
Host: Pennsylvania State University

Andrew Rechnitz

PhD English, The University of Texas
at Austin
Host: Southwestern University

Christopher Sawula

PhD History, Emory University
Host: University of Alabama

Meridith Beck Sayre

PhD History of Science,
University of Wisconsin-Madison
Host: Indiana University

Emily Sherwood

PhD English, The City University of
New York
Host: Bucknell University

Stephanie Simms

PhD Archaeology, Boston University
Host: University of California, Los
Angeles

Plato Smith

PhD Library and Information Studies,
Florida State University
Host: University of New Mexico

Todd Suomela

PhD Communication and Information,
University of Tennessee
Host: University of Alberta

Yun Tai

PhD Sociology, Emory University
Host: University of Virginia

Ana Van Gulick

PhD Psychology, Vanderbilt
University
Host: Carnegie Mellon University

Continuing Current Fellows

Sayan Bhattacharyya

PhD Comparative Literature,
University of Michigan
Host: University of Illinois at Urbana-
Champaign/HathiTrust Research
Center

Alexandra Bolintineanu

PhD Medieval Studies, University of
Toronto
Host: University of Toronto

Jonathan Cachat

PhD Neuroscience, Tulane University
Host: University of California, Davis

Amy Chen

PhD English, Emory University
Host: University of Alabama

Margarita Corral

PhD Political Science, Vanderbilt
University
Host: Brandeis University

Matthew Davis

PhD English, Texas A&M University
Host: North Carolina State University

Jodi Flores

PhD Archaeology, University of
Exeter, England
Host: Arizona State University

Nikolaus Fogle

PhD Philosophy, Temple University
Host: Villanova University

John Kratz

PhD Biological Sciences, Columbia
University
Host: California Digital Library

The Postdoctoral Fellows summer seminar at Bryn Mawr

(Fellows contd.)

Katie Rawson

PhD Institute of Liberal Arts, Emory University
Host: University of Pennsylvania

Kendall Roark

PhD Anthropology, Temple University
Host: University of Alberta

Tamsyn Rose-Steel

PhD Medieval Studies, University of Exeter, England
Host: Johns Hopkins University

Justin Schell

PhD Comparative Studies in Discourse and Society, University of Minnesota
Host: University of Minnesota

Matthew Sisk

PhD Anthropology, Stony Brook University
Host: University of Notre Dame

Colleen Strawhacker

PhD Anthropology, Arizona State University
Host: University of Colorado at Boulder/National Snow and Ice Data Center

Ece Turnator

PhD History, Harvard University
Host: University of Texas-Austin

Bridget Whearty

PhD English Literature, Stanford University
Host: Stanford University

Donna Wrublewski

PhD Polymer Science & Engineering, University of Massachusetts, Amherst
Host: California Institute of Technology

2014–2015 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Oscar Aguirre-Mandujano

University of Washington
Captured by Writing: Literary Language and Political Culture in the Court of Bayezid II (r.1481-1512)

Elisabeth Burton

Harvard University
Genetic Nationalism: Ethnic Mythmaking and Human Biology Research in Iran, Turkey, and Israel

Samuel Fury Childs Daly

Columbia University
Forging Nigerian Citizenship: Law and Bureaucracy in the Biafra War, 1967-1970

Alexander Eastman

Washington University in St. Louis
Binding Freedom: Cuba's Black Public Sphere, 1868-1912

Edward Falk

University of California, San Diego
"Peaceful Conquest Through Education": Missionary Education in Ottoman Syria

Devin McGeehan Muchmore

Yale University
"It's All for Sale": Erotic Entrepreneurs and the Moral Economies of Sexual Commerce in the Late-Twentieth Century United States

Stuart McManus

Harvard University
Globalizing Cicero: Humanist Eloquence in Early Modern European Empires

Emma Otheguy

New York University
Facing the Gallego: Indirect Creolization in the Sixteenth and Seventeenth-Century Atlantic

Bernadette Perez

University of Minnesota, Twin Cities
Beets Better than Gold: Labor, Race, Nation, and the Politics of Belonging in the Development of Colorado Agribusiness

Michael Polczynski

Georgetown University
Antemurale Christianitatis, Memâlik-i Mahrûse: the "Bulwark of Christendom" and the "Well Protected Domains" of the Early Modern Polish-Lithuanian/Ottoman Frontier

Paolo Savoia

Harvard University
Saving Faces: Surgery, Masculinity, and the History of the Human Face in Early Modern Italy

Amanda Scott

Washington University in St. Louis
The Basque Seroras: Local Religion, Gender and Power in Northern Iberia, 1550-1800

Kathleen Tahk

Northwestern University
A Revolution Beyond Borders: The Soviet Art of the Latvian Riflemen, 1917-1938

Lucy Traverse

University of Wisconsin-Madison
Ectoplasmic Modernities: Materialization Photography at the Turn of the Century

Benjamin Weber

Harvard University
America's Carceral Empire: Punishment, Work and Detention at "Home" and Abroad, 1865-1945

Elizabeth Woodward

University of Chicago
"Le Roman de la Poire": Constructing Courtliness and "Courtly" Art in Gothic France

Ahyoung Yoo

The Ohio State University
"We Are In Open Circuits": Technology, Globalization, and Contemporary Korean Art

ADVISORY GROUPS

as of June 30, 2014

Digital Library Federation Advisory Committee

Patricia Hswe
Pennsylvania State University

Max Marmor
Samuel H. Kress Foundation

Trevor Muñoz
University of Maryland Libraries

Stephen Rhind-Tutt
Alexander Street Press

David Rumsey
David Rumsey Map Collection and
Cartography Associates

Bess Sadler
Stanford University Library

Sarah Shreeves
IDEALS and Scholarly Commons

Winston Tabb
Johns Hopkins University

Jennifer Vinopal
New York University

2013 Hidden Collections Review Panel Final Proposal Phase, *and*

2014 Hidden Collections Review Panel Initial Proposal Phase

Michael Edson
Director, Web and New Media Strategy
Smithsonian Institution

Rachel Frick
Director, Digital Library Federation
Program
CLIR

Charles Henry
President
CLIR

Mary Kelley
Professor of History
University of Michigan

Ronald L. Larsen
Dean and Professor, School of
Information Sciences
University of Pittsburgh

Jerome McGann
John Stewart Bryan University Professor
University of Virginia

Dennis Meissner
Head of Collections Management
Minnesota Historical Society

Stephen G. Nichols
James M. Beall Professor of French and
Humanities
Johns Hopkins University

Cheryl Oestericher
Head of Special Collections and Archives/
Assistant Professor
Boise State University

Lynn Ransom
Project Manager, Lawrence J. Schoenberg
Database of Manuscripts
The University of Pennsylvania Libraries

Lisa Spiro
Executive Director, Digital Scholarship
Services
Rice University

Richard V. Szary
Director, Louis Round Wilson Library
and Associate University Librarian for
Special Collections
University of North Carolina at Chapel
Hill

Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Sources, Selection Committee for 2014–2015 Fellows

Elena Jackson Albarrán
Miami University

Andrew Asher
Indiana University Bloomington

Alan Barenberg
Texas Tech University

Mark Dimunation
Library of Congress

Charles Henry
CLIR

Michelle King
The University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Miriam Posner
University of California, Los Angeles

Heather Waldroup
Appalachian State University

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

**FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

**FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2014
WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT**

**STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia**

Council on Library and Information Resources

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STONE AND SPRING
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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
Stephen C. Stone, C.P.A.

INDEPENDENT AUDITOR'S REPORT

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, DC

We have audited the accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources (a non-profit organization), which comprise the statement of financial position as of June 30, 2014, and the related statements of activities and change in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended, and the related notes to the financial statements.

Management's Responsibility for the Financial Statements

Management is responsible for the preparation and fair presentation of these financial statements in accordance with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America; this includes the design, implementation, and maintenance of internal control relevant to the preparation and fair presentation of financial statements that are free from material misstatement, whether due to fraud or error.

Auditor's Responsibility

Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit. We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free from material misstatement.

An audit involves performing procedures to obtain audit evidence about the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. The procedures selected depend on the auditor's judgment, including the assessment of the risks of material misstatement of the financial statements, whether due to fraud or error. In making those risk assessments, the auditor considers internal control relevant to the entity's preparation and fair presentation of the financial statements in order to design audit procedures that are appropriate in the circumstances, but not for the purpose of expressing an opinion on the effectiveness of the entity's internal control. Accordingly, we express no such opinion. An audit also includes evaluating the appropriateness of accounting policies used and the reasonableness of significant accounting estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall presentation of the financial statements.

We believe that the audit evidence we have obtained is sufficient and appropriate to provide a basis for our audit opinion.

Opinion

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2014, and the change in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in accordance with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Other Matter

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the financial statements as a whole. The schedule of functional expenses on page 33 is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the financial statements. Such information is the responsibility of management and was derived from and relates directly to the underlying accounting and other records used to prepare the financial statements. The information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the financial statements and certain additional procedures, including comparing and reconciling such information directly to the underlying accounting and other records used to prepare the financial statements or to the financial statements themselves, and other additional procedures in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. In our opinion, the information is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the financial statements as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
September 03, 2014

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2014

	Unrestricted	Temporary Restricted	Total
Current Assets:			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 635,893	\$ 7,686,322	\$ 8,322,215
Investments	120,195	2,163,853	2,284,048
Accounts receivable	11,498	21,613	33,111
Total current assets	<u>\$ 767,586</u>	<u>\$ 9,871,788</u>	<u>\$ 10,639,374</u>
Furniture and equipment, net of accumulated depreciation	<u>\$ 30,878</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 30,878</u>
Other assets	75,718	-	75,718
Total Assets	<u>\$ 874,182</u>	<u>\$ 9,871,788</u>	<u>\$ 10,745,970</u>
Current Liabilities:			
Accounts payable	\$ 429,421	\$ -	\$ 429,421
Capital lease payable	3,092	-	3,092
Accrued expenses	85,252	-	85,252
Total Current Liabilities	<u>\$ 517,765</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 517,765</u>
Long Term Liabilities:			
Capital lease payable, net of current portion	<u>\$ 13,874</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 13,874</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 531,639</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 531,639</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 342,543</u>	<u>\$ 9,871,788</u>	<u>\$ 10,214,331</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u><u>\$ 874,182</u></u>	<u><u>\$ 9,871,788</u></u>	<u><u>\$ 10,745,970</u></u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2014

	Unrestricted	Temporary Restricted	Total
Revenue			
Grants and contracts	\$ -	\$ 8,546,707	\$ 8,546,707
Contributions	1,043,340	2,500	1,045,840
Publication sales	789	-	789
Investment income	16,923	45,042	61,965
Other income	411,343	6,015	417,358
	<u>\$ 1,472,395</u>	<u>\$ 8,600,264</u>	<u>\$ 10,072,659</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions			
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 7,380,025</u>	<u>\$ (7,380,025)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 8,852,420</u>	<u>\$ 1,220,239</u>	<u>\$ 10,072,659</u>
Expenses			
Program services:			
Preservation and access	\$ 4,336,792	\$ -	\$ 4,336,792
Digital infrastructure	733,184	-	733,184
Leadership, education and cultivation	199,780	-	199,780
Other strategic initiatives	73,822	-	73,822
Communications and publications	379,513	-	379,513
Outreach and collaboration	356,980	-	356,980
Scholarship and research	2,125,422	-	2,125,422
Total Program Services	<u>\$ 8,205,493</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 8,205,493</u>
Administration	<u>\$ 520,134</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 520,134</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 8,725,627</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 8,725,627</u>
Change in Net Assets	\$ 126,793	\$ 1,220,239	\$ 1,347,032
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>215,750</u>	<u>8,651,549</u>	<u>8,867,299</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 342,543</u>	<u>\$ 9,871,788</u>	<u>\$ 10,214,331</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the year ended June 30, 2014

Operating Activities	
Change in net assets	\$ 1,347,032
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) operating activities:	
Depreciation	12,959
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	(12,604)
(Increase) decrease in other assets	32,326
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	14,715
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	226,338
	<hr/>
Net Cash Provided (used) by Operating Activities	\$ 1,620,766
Investing Activities	
Purchases of investments	\$ (1,829,500)
Sales of investments	1,509,580
Disposal of furniture and equipment	1,296
Purchases of furniture and equipment	(24,631)
	<hr/>
Net Cash Provided (Used) by Investing Activities	\$ (343,255)
Financing Activities	
Principal payments on capital lease	\$ (3,654)
Proceeds from notes payable	17,704
Net Cash Provided (Used) by Financing Activities	\$ 14,050
	<hr/>
Net Change in Cash and Cash equivalents	\$ 1,291,561
Cash and Cash Equivalents, Beginning of Year	<hr/> 7,030,654
Cash and Cash Equivalents, End of Year	<hr/> <hr/> \$ 8,322,215
Supplemental Cash Flow Information:	
Interest paid during the year	<hr/> \$ 402

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2014

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council on Library and Information Resources is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council on Library and Information Resources operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council on Library and Information Resources conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council on Library and Information Resources reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council on Library and Information Resources are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs – Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2014
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent grant receivable, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council on Library and Information Resources management has evaluated accounts receivable collection from prior years and has determined that an allowance for doubtful accounts is not necessary.

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council on Library and Information Resources records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments – Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2014 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

Subsequent Events- In preparing these financial statements, The Council on Library and Information Resources has evaluated events and transactions for potential recognition or disclosure through September 3, 2014, the date the financial statements were issued.

NOTE 3- Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

Furniture and equipment	\$ 95,615
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(64,737)</u>
	<u>\$ 30,878</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2014
(Continued)

NOTE 4- Investments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has adopted SFAS No. 124, "Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations." Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2014

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -
Bonds	-	-	-
Corporate fixed income	-	-	-
Government securities	-	-	-
Certificates of deposit	(12,394)	(4,512)	1,761,387
Mutual funds	-	17,116	522,661
Subtotal	<u>\$ (12,394)</u>	<u>\$ 12,604</u>	<u>\$ 2,284,048</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	-	-	<u>\$ 8,322,215</u>
Total	<u>\$ (12,394)</u>	<u>\$ 12,604</u>	

The following schedule summarizes the investment and cash equivalent return and its classification in the statement of activities for the year ended June 30, 2014:

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	Temporarily <u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Interest and dividends	\$ 14,425	\$ 47,330	\$ 61,755
Realized gains (losses)	(12,394)	-	(12,394)
Unrealized gains (losses)	<u>14,892</u>	<u>(2,288)</u>	<u>12,604</u>
Total investment return	<u>\$ 16,923</u>	<u>\$ 45,042</u>	<u>\$ 61,965</u>

NOTE 5 - Income Taxes

The Council on Library and Information Resources is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2014
(Continued)

NOTE 5 - Income Taxes (Continued)

The Organization is subject to income taxes in U.S. federal jurisdictions and various state jurisdictions. Tax regulations within each jurisdiction are subject to the interpretation of the related tax laws and regulations and require significant judgment to apply. In accordance with authoritative guidance on accounting for uncertainty in income taxes issued by the Financial Accounting Standards Board (the FASB), the Organization recognizes tax liabilities for uncertain tax positions when it is more likely than not that a tax position will not be sustained upon examination and settlement with various taxing authorities. Liabilities for uncertain tax positions are measured based upon the largest amount of benefit that is greater than 50% likely of being realized upon settlement. The guidance on accounting for uncertainty in income taxes also addresses de-recognition, classification, interest and penalties on income taxes, and accounting in interim periods. Management has evaluated the Organization's tax positions and has concluded that the Organization has no uncertain tax positions that require adjustment to the financial statements to comply with the provisions of this guidance. Income taxes are accounted for under the asset and liability method. Management believes it is no longer subject to income tax examinations for years prior to June 30, 2011.

NOTE 6 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 7 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council on Library and Information Resources defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council on Library and Information Resources contributions. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributions were \$158,441 in 2014.

NOTE 8 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council on Library and Information Resources to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2014, the Council on Library and Information Resources held \$2,284,048 in investments. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in bank and investment accounts are insured under FDIC up to \$250,000 for each bank. At June 30, 2014, the uninsured cash balance was \$7,888,548

The Council on Library and Information Resources received \$4,350,000, \$1,832,000, and \$1,400,000 for three grant programs which represents 43 %, 18%, and 14% of total revenue respectively.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2014
(Continued)

NOTE 9 – Accounts Receivable	June 30, <u>2014</u>
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 27,558
30 – 60 days	5,553
60 – 90 days	-
Over 90 days	-
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u>-</u>
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>\$ 33,111</u>

NOTE 10 - Commitments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into two noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August, 2018 and April, 2019. The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into a sublease with another organization that it collects rent from which expires August, 2018. Rental expense, for the year ending June 30, 2014 was \$139,977. The Council on Library and Information Resources is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in March 2019.

Future minimum lease payments under all leases net of amounts collected from subtenant with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending <u>June 30,</u>	Capital <u>Lease</u>	Operating <u>Leases</u>	Subtenant <u>Lease</u>	Net Operating <u>Leases</u>
2015	\$ 4,260	\$ 405,832	\$ (252,736)	\$ 153,096
2016	4,260	418,944	(261,582)	157,362
2017	4,260	432,489,	(270,738)	161,751
2018	4,260	446,479	(280,214)	166,265
2019	3,195	155,780	(48,057)	107,723
2020 and beyond	-	-	(-)	-
Total minimum lease payments	<u>\$ 20,235</u>	<u>\$1,859,524</u>	<u>\$ (1,113,327)</u>	<u>\$ 746,197</u>
Less: Amount representing interest.	<u>(3,269)</u>			
Present value of net minimum lease payments	<u>\$ 16,966</u>			

NOTE 11- Board Designated Net Assets Funds

The Board of Directors voted to designate net assets of \$400,000 for operating reserves.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2014

(Concluded)

NOTE 12 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments

The carrying amounts reflected in the balance sheets for cash, cash equivalents, loans and notes payable approximate the respective fair values due to the short maturities of those instruments. SFAS 157 requires a fair value hierarchy to be used to prioritize valuation inputs into three levels:

Level 1 – Quoted prices (unadjusted) in active markets for identical assets or liabilities.

Level 2 – Observable inputs other than the quoted prices included in Level 1.

Level 3 – Unobservable inputs.

Fair values of assets and liabilities measured on a nonrecurring basis at June 30, 2014 are as follows:

	Fair Value	(Level 1)	(Level 2)	(Level 3)	(Losses)
Description					
Long-lived assets held for sale	\$ 2,284,048	—	\$ 2,284,048	\$ -	-

Long-lived assets have been valued using a market approach. The values were determined using market prices of similar long-lived assets.

NOTE 13 – Other Income

Other income consists of the following:

Leading Change Institute Fees	\$ 195,000
Fellowship and Speaker Fees	55,428
Registration Fees	130,625
Webinar and other fees	<u>36,305</u>
Total Other Income	<u>\$ 417,358</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
 SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
 For The Year Ended June 30, 2014

	Digital Infrastructure	Outreach and Collaboration	Leadership, Education, and Cultivation	Preservation and Access	Other Strategic Initiatives	Scholarship and Research	Communications and Publications	Total Program	Administration	Total
Employee costs	\$ 404,258	\$ 125,812	\$ 27,368	\$ 267,311	\$ 71,986	\$ 287,863	\$ 288,002	\$ 1,472,600	\$ 186,893	\$ 1,659,493
Professional Services and contracts	40,103	-	20,000	35,062	-	106,815	2,600	204,580	38,296	242,876
Fellowships, scholarships and interns	11,925	-	-	-	-	1,465,885	-	1,477,810	-	1,477,810
Grants Awarded	-	-	-	3,950,300	-	-	-	3,950,300	-	3,950,300
Grants Returned	-	-	-	-	-	-	45,408	45,408	-	45,408
Communications	11,398	5,934	1,761	8,426	-	22,198	14,489	64,206	44,176	108,382
Travel and meetings	232,220	209,677	148,338	64,807	1,836	206,956	5,108	868,942	63,679	932,621
Publications	2,284	225	8	25	-	22	21,109	23,673	-	23,673
Registration management fees	3,474	-	29	-	-	-	-	3,503	-	3,503
Office operations	11,543	9,663	2,276	3,175	-	4,331	2,797	33,785	247,776	281,561
Indirect	15,979	5,669	-	7,686	-	31,352	-	60,686	(60,686)	-
Total	\$ 733,184	\$ 356,980	\$ 199,780	\$ 4,336,792	\$ 73,822	\$ 2,125,422	\$ 379,513	\$ 8,205,493	\$ 520,134	\$ 8,725,627

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.